

Naphthalene Ring and Sugden's Parachors. Part III.

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Macleod (*Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1923, **19**, 38) has shown that over a wide range of substances the relationship given below holds :

$$y = C(D-d)^4$$

where y is the surface-tension in dynes/cm., D and d , the densities of the substance and its vapour respectively, and C , the Macleod's constant. From this it follows that $C = y/(D-d)^4$.

If the fourth root of the Macleod constant be multiplied by the molecular weight (M), the following expression is obtained : -

$$P = \sqrt[4]{C} \times M = \frac{M}{(D-d)} \times y^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad \dots (1)$$

The quantity $M/(D-d)$ has the dimensions of volume, and at low temperatures, where d becomes very small, this represents, in fact, the molecular volume. The quantity (P) has been named as the "Parachor" by Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1177). He has shown that this molecular parachor is an additive product of its atomic and structural parachors, the values for most of which have been obtained by him.

In a previous paper (*J. Chim. phys.*, 1928, **25**, 21) the authors calculated the value for the parachor of the naphthalene structure as 9.3 by the formula $23.2x/n$ (Sugden and Wilkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **131**, 139), where x represents the number of latent valencies and n the number of octets in the structure.

In a private communication Sugden suggested that the value for the parachor of the naphthalene ring might be best represented if we take it to be as composed of two separate six-membered rings. On this viewpoint the value of the naphthalene ring would be $2 \times 6.1 = 12.2$, where 6.1 is the value of the parachor for the benzene ring.

The present investigation was undertaken to test the validity of Sugden's suggestion on data previously described and from the values of surface tension of naphthalene compounds now determined by the authors.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The determination of the parachor involves the measurement of surface tension and density at a series of temperatures; the parachor is then calculated by the formula (1). For the substances described below, d was calculated by the method of Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 129, 1525) and found to be very small at the temperature of observation and has been neglected. Densities were determined with a U-shaped pyknometer (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1167) and surface tension by the maximum bubble pressure method with an apparatus previously described by the authors (*loc. cit.*). The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Temperature.	Density, gms./c.c.	Surface tension, dynes/cm.	Parachor (P) obs.
Naphthalene.	80.1°	0.9765	32.26	312.5
Acenaphthene.	128.6°	1.0020	31.36	364.1
	178.7°	0.9610	26.60	364.2
α -Chloro-naphthalene.	20°	1.1706	41.80	353.0
α -Bromo-naphthalene.	13.6°	1.488	45.97	362.3
	33.4°	1.470	43.96	362.6
	50.0°	1.454	42.13	362.6
	83.5°	1.425	38.92	362.8
				Mean = 362.6
α -Naphthol.	100.5°	1.163	38.88	326.2
	116.8°	1.090	37.16	326.4
	134.7°	1.076	35.51	327.0
				Mean = 326.5
β -Naphthol.	130.2°	1.078	36.45	328.3
	144.5°	1.067	35.14	328.6
	161.0°	1.055	33.70	329.0
				Mean = 328.6
α -Naphthylamine.	54.3°	1.100	47.25	341.0
	67.5°	1.090	45.81	341.5
	61.4°	1.079	44.16	341.8
	96.0°	1.068	42.52	342.2
				Mean = 341.6
β -Naphthylamine.	115.8°	1.049	39.29	341.5
	130.2°	1.039	37.91	341.8
	142.0°	1.031	36.87	342.0
				Mean = 341.8

The values of surface tension for naphthalene, acenaphthene and α -chloronaphthalene are taken from the following papers: -

1. Naphthalene (Bhatnagar and Singh, *J. Chim. phys.*, 1928, 25, 21).
2. Acenaphthene (Dutoit and Friedrich, *Arch. Sci. phys. nat.*, 1900, 9, 105).
3. α -Chloro-naphthalene (Harkins and Feldman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2665).

The naphthylamines were distilled and their surface tension determined in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

The values of the parachors for the above substances are calculated from the values of the various atomic and structural constants of Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1187, and subsequent papers) assigning 12.2 and 9.3 as the value of the parachor for the naphthalene ring, where 12.2 is the value suggested privately by Sugden on the concept that the value for the ring constant is twice that found for the benzene ring, and 9.3 is the value calculated by the authors (*loc. cit.*). The value for OH group is taken from a previous paper of the authors (*loc. cit.*).

The values of the parachor (P)_{cal. 12.2} and (P)_{cal. 9.3} calculated, taking 12.2 and 9.3 respectively as the value for the ring constant, are compared with the values of the parachors (P)_{obs.} obtained from the surface tension data in Table II.

TABLE II.

Substance.	Parachor observed: (P) _{obs.}	Parachor (P) _{cal. 12.2}	Parachor (P) _{cal. 9.3}
Naphthalene.	312.5	313.0	310.1
Acenaphthene.	364.2	365.3	362.4
α -Chloro-naphthalene.	353.0	350.2	347.3
α -Bromo-naphthalene.	362.6	363.9	361.0
α -Naphthol.	326.5	326.3	323.4
β -Naphthol.	328.6	326.3	323.4
α -Naphthylamine.	341.6	342.6	339.7
β -Naphthylamine.	341.8	342.6	339.7

From the above table it is evident that the values of the parachors calculated with 12.2 as the ring constant for naphthalene

are in better agreement with the observed parachors than the values calculated with 9.3 as the ring-constant.

The ring-constant for naphthalene, therefore, is the sum of two six-membered ring-constants ($2 \times 6.1 = 12.2$). This view is also supported by the work on decahydro-naphthalenes (Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 133, 2017) in which case the value for the ring-constant is practically twice that found for the cyclohexane ring.

Summary.

1. Surface tensions and densities of α -bromonaphthalene, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, α -naphthylamine and β -naphthylamine have been determined at various temperatures.

2. Parachors for these substances have been calculated from the observed data as well as from the values of atomic and structural parachors.

3. The value of the parachor for naphthalene ring has been found to be 12.2.

In conclusion the authors wish to express their indebtedness to Dr. S. Sugden for his valuable suggestion.